

Lemmel Syndrome Causing Obstructive Jaundice: A Rare Presentation of Periapillary Duodenal Diverticulum Managed by Surgical Decompression – A Case Report

Min Nay Zar Wyke*¹, Min Htet San², Soe Htut Aung², Aung Ko Ko Linn², Kyaw Thu Linn², Thant Lwyn San³, Khin Aung Htun⁴

¹Senior Consultant Surgeon, No. (1) Military Hospital (700-Bedded), Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar.

¹<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-0986-1047>

²Consultant Surgeon, No. (1) Military Hospital (700-Bedded), Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar.

³Professor and Head of Department of Surgery, Defence Services Medical Academy, Yangon, Myanmar.

⁴Rector and Senior Consultant Surgeon, Defence Services Medical Academy, Yangon, Myanmar.

ABSTRACT

Background: Lemmel syndrome is a rare cause of obstructive jaundice resulting from extrinsic compression of the common bile duct (CBD) by a periampullary duodenal diverticulum. It occurs in the absence of choledocholithiasis or malignancy and is frequently overlooked due to its nonspecific clinical presentation.

Case Presentation: A 74-year-old male presented with progressive jaundice, intermittent fever, pruritus, dyspepsia, and upper abdominal discomfort for one month. Initial investigations demonstrated biliary dilatation without evidence of choledocholithiasis. Contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CECT) and endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) demonstrated a large periampullary duodenal diverticulum compressing the distal CBD, consistent with Lemmel syndrome. Despite endoscopic therapy and medical management, the patient developed persistent cholangitis and worsening jaundice. Surgical exploration was performed, and cholecystectomy with choledochotomy, CBD stent insertion, and peritoneal toileting were carried out. No gallstones or CBD stones were identified intraoperatively. The postoperative course was uneventful, with progressive normalization of liver function tests and resolution of jaundice.

Conclusion: Lemmel syndrome is an uncommon but important differential diagnosis in elderly patients with obstructive jaundice. Awareness of this entity and appropriate imaging are essential for early diagnosis. Endoscopic therapy is the preferred initial approach, but surgical intervention provides effective treatment when endoscopic management fails.

KEYWORDS: Lemmel syndrome, periampullary duodenal diverticulum, obstructive jaundice, biliary obstruction, ERCP, surgical management.

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INTRODUCTION

Obstructive jaundice is a common clinical condition with a wide range of etiologies, most frequently gallstones, malignant strictures, and pancreaticobiliary tumors. However, uncommon benign causes must also be considered when routine investigations fail to reveal an obvious pathology. One such rare cause is compression of the

common bile duct (CBD) by a periampullary duodenal diverticulum, known as Lemmel syndrome (1).

Periapillary duodenal diverticula are mucosal outpouchings arising within 2-3 cm of the ampulla of Vater. These diverticula are relatively common in the elderly population, with an increasing prevalence reported with advancing age (2). Despite their frequency, the majority

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remain asymptomatic and are detected incidentally during endoscopic or radiological investigations.

In rare circumstances, a periampullary diverticulum may cause extrinsic compression of the distal CBD, leading to biliary obstruction in the absence of choledocholithiasis or malignancy. This clinical entity was first described by Gerhard Lemmel in 1934 and later termed “Lemmel syndrome” (1). The underlying mechanism of obstruction may involve direct mechanical compression, chronic inflammatory changes, or sphincter of Oddi dysfunction (3). The clinical presentation of Lemmel syndrome is often nonspecific and can closely mimic more common causes of biliary obstruction. Patients may present with jaundice, abdominal pain, cholangitis, or pancreatitis, making early diagnosis challenging (4). Because of this overlap, the condition is frequently overlooked in routine clinical practice.

Imaging modalities play a crucial role in diagnosis. Ultrasonography can detect biliary dilatation but is limited in identifying periampullary diverticula. Contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CECT), magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP), and particularly endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) are more effective in confirming the diagnosis and guiding management (5,6).

Although endoscopic management is considered first-line therapy, surgical intervention may be required in patients with persistent obstruction or failed endoscopic treatment (7). Awareness of this rare entity is essential to avoid misdiagnosis and to provide timely and appropriate management. This report presents a rare case of Lemmel syndrome in an elderly male patient who developed obstructive jaundice due to a large periampullary diverticulum and was successfully treated with surgical intervention after failure of endoscopic therapy.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 74-year-old male was admitted with complaints of progressive yellow discoloration of the skin and sclera for one month. The symptoms were associated with intermittent fever, nausea, vomiting, generalized itching, and upper abdominal discomfort. He also reported mild exertional dyspnea but denied chest pain, weight loss, hematemesis, or melena.

Figure 1. Axial CECT abdomen showing a distended gallbladder with dilated CBD and a periampullary duodenal diverticulum compressing the distal CBD.

There was no prior history of gallstone disease, alcohol consumption, or previous abdominal surgery. The patient had no known malignancy or chronic liver disease. On examination, he was alert with stable vital signs. Blood pressure was 90/70 mmHg, pulse rate 92/min, and oxygen saturation 99% on room air. Icterus was present, but there was no pallor, peripheral edema or lymphadenopathy. Abdominal examination revealed a soft, non-tender abdomen with normal bowel sounds and no palpable masses or organomegaly.

Laboratory investigations demonstrated elevated total and direct bilirubin levels with cholestatic pattern of liver enzyme derangement. Hematological and renal parameters were within normal limits. Echocardiography revealed an ejection fraction of 68%, normal valves and chambers, no pulmonary hypertension, Grade I diastolic dysfunction, and mild left ventricular hypertrophy. Chest radiography showed no abnormal findings.

Figure 2. Axial CECT abdomen showing a dilated CBD with adjacent periampullary duodenal diverticulum.

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Figure 3. Axial CECT abdomen showing a periampullary duodenal diverticulum near the distal CBD, consistent with Lemmel syndrome.

Ultrasonography of the abdomen revealed dilatation of the common bile duct measuring 1.6 cm with dilated intrahepatic biliary radicals. The gallbladder was overdistended with sludge, but no definite stones were visualized. Contrast-enhanced CT scan of the abdomen showed a large periampullary duodenal diverticulum compressing the distal CBD, causing proximal biliary dilatation. No pancreatic or periampullary mass was detected. These radiological findings were consistent with Lemmel syndrome (Figures 1–5).

Figure 4. Sagittal CECT abdomen showing intrahepatic and extrahepatic biliary dilatation caused by external compression of the distal CBD by a periampullary duodenal diverticulum.

Figure 5. Sagittal CECT abdomen showing a dilated CBD with adjacent periampullary duodenal diverticulum.

Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy demonstrated mild esophagitis and gastritis (Figure 6). ERCP confirmed a large periampullary diverticulum with narrowing of the distal CBD and impaired bile flow. Endoscopic decompression was attempted. Despite endoscopic therapy and intravenous antibiotics, the patient continued to experience persistent jaundice and recurrent fever, indicating unresolved biliary obstruction. After multidisciplinary evaluation and optimization, surgical intervention was planned.

Figure 6. Endoscopic views showing mild oesophagitis, antral gastritis, and a periampullary duodenal diverticulum in the second part of the duodenum.

Intraoperative exploration revealed a cholestatic congested liver consistent with prolonged biliary obstruction. The gallbladder was found to be massively distended and

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contained approximately 400 ml of infected bile, but no gallstones were present (Figure 9). The common bile duct was markedly dilated, measuring about 2 cm in diameter, and careful exploration confirmed the absence of intraluminal calculi. A large periampullary duodenal diverticulum measuring approximately 3 × 2 cm was identified at the retroperitoneal portion of the first part of the duodenum, causing significant external compression of the distal common bile duct (Figure 7 & 8). Minimal ascites with bile staining of the peritoneum were also noted.

Figure 7. Intraoperative view of massively distended gall bladder with periampullary duodenal diverticulum adjacent to distal CBD.

Figure 8. Intraoperative view of a massively distended gallbladder consistent with prolonged biliary obstruction caused by periampullary duodenal diverticulum.

Figure 9. Intraoperative view showing needle aspiration and decompression of a massively distended gallbladder.

Surgical management included open cholecystectomy followed by choledochotomy for effective biliary decompression (Figure 10). A common bile duct stent was inserted to ensure adequate postoperative bile drainage (Figure 11 & 12). Peritoneal toileting was performed, and an abdominal drain was placed prior to closure. The procedure was completed without intraoperative complications, and adequate biliary decompression was achieved. No calculi were identified intraoperatively, confirming true Lemmel syndrome.

Figure 10. Intraoperative view of excised gallbladder specimen following cholecystectomy.

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Figure 11. Intraoperative view showing choledochotomy and placement of a CBD stent to relieve biliary obstruction caused by periampullary duodenal diverticulum (Lemmel syndrome).

Figure 12. Intraoperative view showing sutured closure of the common bile duct after stent insertion performed to relieve biliary obstruction in Lemmel syndrome.

Postoperatively, the patient was transferred to the intensive care unit (ICU) for close monitoring and supportive management. He remained hemodynamically stable and received appropriate intravenous antibiotics, fluid therapy, analgesia, and nutritional support under continuous monitoring. After a three-day ICU stay, his clinical condition improved steadily, and he was subsequently shifted to the surgical ward. The patient recovered well with gradual normalization of liver function tests and resolution of jaundice. He was discharged in stable condition and remained asymptomatic on follow-up.

DISCUSSION

Lemmel syndrome is a rare cause of obstructive jaundice produced by external compression of the distal common bile duct (CBD) by a periampullary duodenal diverticulum. Although duodenal diverticula are relatively common in the

elderly population, only a small proportion lead to clinically significant biliary complications (1,2).

The mechanism of biliary obstruction in Lemmel syndrome is multifactorial. Direct mechanical compression of the distal CBD by a large diverticulum is considered the primary cause. Additional contributing factors include chronic inflammatory changes around the diverticulum and dysfunction of the sphincter of Oddi (3). Unlike gallstone disease, Lemmel syndrome characteristically occurs in the absence of calculi, which is a defining feature of this condition (4).

Clinical presentation is usually nonspecific and often resembles other more common biliary disorders such as choledocholithiasis or periampullary malignancy (5). Patients may present with jaundice, abdominal discomfort, fever, pruritus, or recurrent cholangitis. In the present case, the patient presented with progressive jaundice and intermittent fever, which are typical but non-specific symptoms of distal biliary obstruction.

Imaging studies play an essential role in diagnosis. Ultrasonography is usually the initial investigation and typically demonstrates biliary dilatation; however, it cannot reliably identify periampullary diverticula or determine the exact cause of obstruction (6). Cross-sectional imaging with CT scan or magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) is more sensitive in demonstrating the diverticulum and excluding malignant causes of obstruction (7). ERCP remains the gold standard diagnostic modality because it allows direct visualization of the ampullary region and provides therapeutic options (8).

Endoscopic therapy is generally recommended as the initial management approach for Lemmel syndrome. Techniques such as endoscopic sphincterotomy and biliary stent insertion can effectively relieve obstruction in many patients (9). However, large diverticula or distorted anatomy may limit the success of endoscopic procedures, and some patients may fail to respond adequately.

In our patient, persistent biliary obstruction despite ERCP and medical therapy necessitated surgical intervention. Intraoperative findings confirmed the absence of gallstones and CBD stones, supporting the diagnosis of Lemmel syndrome. Surgical management therefore became the definitive treatment in this case.

Surgical intervention remains an effective option in refractory cases or when endoscopic therapy fails. Various surgical procedures have been described, including diverticulectomy, biliary bypass, or CBD decompression with stenting (10). In this case, choledochotomy with CBD stent insertion provided effective decompression and resulted in excellent clinical recovery.

This case highlights the importance of considering Lemmel syndrome in elderly patients with obstructive jaundice when gallstones and malignancy have been excluded. Early recognition, appropriate imaging, and a multidisciplinary

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approach are essential for successful management and favorable outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Lemmel syndrome is a rare but important differential diagnosis of obstructive jaundice. It should be suspected in elderly patients with biliary obstruction without evidence of stones or malignancy. Advanced imaging and ERCP are essential for diagnosis. While endoscopic therapy is preferred, surgical intervention offers effective treatment when endoscopic measures fail. Increased clinical awareness of this entity enables timely diagnosis and appropriate management, thereby preventing unnecessary interventions and improving patient outcomes.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

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